

being through phenolic oxygen atoms of transition metal complexes and alkaline earth metal.

References

1. A. K. BANERJEE, D. PRASAD and S. K. ROY, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1982, 59, 1303.
2. A. SYAMAL and O. P. SINGHAL, *Transition Met. Chem.*, 1979, 4, 179.
3. G. E. BATLEY and D. P. GRADDOM, *Aust. J. Chem.*, 1967, 20, 877.
4. P. L. ORIOLI, M. DIVAIRA and L. SACCONI, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1966, 5, 400.

Complexes of Sulphaguanidine with Copper and Silver

(Miss) SHARDA GARG and S. S. GUPTA

Chemical Laboratories, Motilal Vigyan Mahavidyalaya, Bhopal

Manuscript received 16 May 1984, revised 1 July 1985,
accepted 29 October 1985

IN continuation of our work on sulphonamides¹⁻³ we describe herein complexes of sulphaguanidine with cupric chloride and silver nitrate, keeping this in view that some metal complexes are found to be more potent than their parent sulphonamides. Kaushal and coworkers⁴⁻⁵ have prepared a large number of metal sulphonamide complexes.

Experimental

Composition of the complexes: Standard solution of cupric chloride (0.02 M), silver nitrate (0.02 M) and sulphaguanidine (0.01 M) were prepared in spectroscopically pure ethanol. The ligand solution (10 ml) was diluted to 50 ml and titrated against the metal salt solution using a Toshniwal conductivity bridge and dip type of electrodes at 28°. The results after volume corrections indicate 2 : 1 sulphaguanidine cupric chloride complex and 1 : 1 sulphaguanidine silver nitrate complex, respectively.

Sulphaguanidine-cupric chloride complex: Sulphaguanidine (1.0 g) and cupric chloride (0.4 g) in 2 : 1 molar proportion were dissolved separately in minimum quantity of absolute ethanol. The base solution was added slowly to the metal salt solution with constant stirring. A dark green solution was obtained which on refluxing over

water-bath for 30 min gave a green complex. It was filtered, washed with alcohol and dried (1.1 g), m.p. 185°.

Sulphaguanidine-silver nitrate complex: Sulphaguanidine (1 g) and silver nitrate (0.8 g) in 1 : 1 molar proportions were dissolved separately in minimum quantity of absolute ethanol. The base solution was added slowly to the metal salt solution with constant stirring. A white crystalline complex was obtained, which was filtered, washed with ethanol and dried (1.4 g), m.p. 191°.

Analytical results of the complexes are recorded in Table 1. Nitrogen was estimated by modified Kjeldahl's method⁶, sulphur by Messenger's method and metals by standard volumetric or gravimetric procedures.

Particle size of the complexes and sulphaguanidine was determined by the microscope having eye piece 10 × objective 10 : 1/0.30 and stage micrometer 0.01 mm (Erma, Japan). Particle size was 75-165 for sulphaguanidine with white needle shaped crystals, and 8-15, and 15-30 for sulphaguanidine-cupric chloride and sulphaguanidine-silver nitrate complexes, respectively with green spherical crystals and white rectangular crystals.

Bacteriostatic studies were done by disc method on *Escherichia coli*, *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Bacillus proteus*, *Bacillus pyocyaneus*, *Salmonella typhi* and *Salmonella paratyphi A* pathogens.

Results and Discussion

The conductometric titrations indicate that sulphaguanidine forms 2 : 1 complex with copper, and 1 : 1 complex with silver. Yamabe and coworkers⁷ have reported 2 : 1 ratio for various copper sulpha drug complexes. Turner and coworkers⁸ have suggested 1 : 1 complex of sulphadiazene with silver. Narang and Gupta⁹ have reported 1 : 1 complex of sulphapyridine with silver nitrate.

The present studies are supported by the work of Tskitishvili *et al.*¹⁰ on sulphapyradizine complexes with Cu, Zn, Cd *etc.* In these complexes donation of lone pair of electrons is shown by oxygen of SO₂ group and nitrogen of substituted group of sulphonamide. Sulphaguanidine-cupric chloride and sulphaguanidine-silver nitrate complexes on boiling with water gives test for chloride and nitrate ions which confirms that these ions

TABLE I

Complex	Analysis % : Found/(Calcd.)					
	Metal	Cl/NO ₃	C	H	N	S
(C ₇ H ₁₀ O ₂ N ₄ S) ₂ CuCl ₂	11.21 (11.29)	12.16 (12.57)	29.90 (29.89)	3.31 (3.58)	19.85 (19.92)	11.57 (11.40)
(C ₇ H ₁₀ O ₂ N ₄ S)AgNO ₃	27.98 (28.10)	-	22.70 (21.90)	2.94 (2.62)	14.29 (14.59)	08.18 (08.35)

were attached to the complexes by primary valency. The structures are supported by ir spectral data. Metal-nitrogen frequencies were observed at 640 and 635 cm^{-1} in sulphaguanidine-cupric chloride and sulphaguanidine-silver nitrate, respectively. Similarly, metal-oxygen frequencies were observed at $685 \pm 5 \text{ cm}^{-1}$. Two bands were observed near 3430 and 3330 cm^{-1} of strong and very strong intensity in the ligand with Cu and Ag complexes, indicating that aniline NH_2 group is not altered in any way. A characteristic frequency at 1570 cm^{-1} was observed indicating the formation of a six-membered heterocyclic ring. Strong vibration of ligand is modified to weak or medium in complexes.

It is observed that particle size of sulphaguanidine complexes is smaller than sulphaguanidine. This indicates that metal complexes are capable of being absorbed more readily than sulphaguanidine.

Bacteriostatic studies of complexes were carried out using *E. coli*, *S. aureus*, *B. proteus*, *B. pyocyaneus*, *S. typhi* and *S. paratyphi* A. Results indicate that copper complex is slightly reactive on *S. paratyphi*, resistance on *B. pyocyaneus* and very slightly reactive on other pathogens. Silver complex is mildly reactive on *S. aureus*, *B. pyocyaneus*, *S. typhi* and slightly reactive on other pathogens, while sulphaguanidine is resistant to all pathogens.

Acknowledgement

The authors are thankful to the Principal, Motilal Vigyan Mahavidyalaya, Bhopal, for facilities, to C.D.R.I., Lucknow, for analyses, and to I.D.P.L., Hyderabad, for the gift of sulphaguanidine. One of the authors (S.G.) is grateful to C.S.I.R., New Delhi, for a Junior Research Fellowship, while the other (S.S.G.) to U.G.C., New Delhi, for financial support.

References

1. S. GARG, V. S. PATEL and S. S. GUPTA, *J. Sci. Res.*, 1982, 4, 135.
2. S. GARG, V. S. PATEL and S. S. GUPTA, *Vijnana Parishad Anusandhan Patrika*, 1983, 26, 73.
3. S. GARG, V. S. PATEL and S. S. GUPTA, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1983, 60, 289.
4. K. K. PANDEY and R. KAUSHAL, *Indian J. Appl. Ch. m.*, 1969, 32, 96.
5. K. K. CHATURVEDI and R. KAUSHAL, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1970, 47, 1135.
6. M. ASHRAF, *Talanta*, 1968, 15, 559.
7. S. YAMABE, *Chem. Abstr.*, 1962, 56, 10291.
8. S. E. TURNER and MICHAEL, *J. Chem. Soc., Perkin Trans. 2*, 1975, 1021.
9. K. K. NARANG and J. K. GUPTA, *J. Sci. Res., Banaras Hindu Univ.*, 1977-78, 28, 109.
10. M. G. TSKITISHVILI, P. V. GOGORISHVILI, M. V. CHRELASTIVILI and A. E. SHVELASHVILI, *Izv. Akad. Nauk Gruz. SSR, Ser. Khim.*, 1979, 5, 13.

Complexes of Zinc(II), Cadmium(II) and Mercury(II) with 2-Thio-3-benzoylhydantoin

S. SHARMA*

Department of Chemistry, S. S. College, Jehanabad
and

M. KUMAR and T. SHARMA

Inorganic Research Laboratory, P. G. Department of Chemistry, Bihar University, Muzaffarpur

Manuscript received 9 March 1984, revised 25 March 1985,
accepted 29 October 1985

SEVERAL complexes of Zn^{2+} , Cd^{2+} and Hg^{2+} with nitrogen donors have been reported^{1,2}.

Some complexes of group II B metals have also been reported in which the ligand coordinates through sulphur as well as nitrogen³. Some workers⁴ have also studied the variation of M—N and M—O stretching frequencies in complexes of Zn^{2+} , Cd^{2+} and Hg^{2+} . However, complexes of these metals with ligands containing sulphur, nitrogen and oxygen donors together have not been studied. Hence, it appeared worthwhile to study the chelating behaviour of 2-thio-3-benzoylhydantoin (TBHNH) with Zn^{2+} , Cd^{2+} and Hg^{2+} .

Experimental

The ligand was prepared by a literature method⁵. For the preparation of metal chelates, a hot ethanolic solution of the metal chloride and that of ligand were mixed in 1 : 2 molar ratio and the resulting solution was refluxed for 2 h. The zinc complex precipitated immediately. The cadmium and mercury complexes precipitated when pH of the solution was raised to 8 by adding dilute sodium hydroxide solution. The precipitate formed was washed successively with water, alcohol and ether. It was dried in a desiccator.

Results and Discussion

Analytical data of the three chelates have been given in Table 1.

Molar conductivity was measured in acetone solution. Molar conductivity value of Zn^{2+} chelate falls in the range of 1 : 2 electrolytes⁶, whereas Cd^{2+} and Hg^{2+} chelates are non-electrolytes. All the three compounds are diamagnetic as expected.

Infrared spectrum of the ligand exhibits several absorption bands. A medium band at 3280 cm^{-1} is assigned to stretching vibration of NH group⁷. In the region 1750-1600 cm^{-1} , the ligand displays two bands, one very strong at 1740 cm^{-1} and the other at 1690 cm^{-1} which are assignable to C = O of $\text{C}_6\text{H}_5\text{C}=\text{O}$ and the other to C = O group⁸, respectively of the ligand. The strong absorption at 1450 cm^{-1} may be assigned¹⁰ to C = S.